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RESULTS OF GAS-HYDRODYNAMIC AND THERMODYNAMIC STUDIES OF WELLS AND FORMATIONS FOR DUAL COMPLETION OF WELLS ON THE ALTYGUYI FIELD

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Abstract

The article presents the results of gas-hydrodynamic and thermodynamic studies of wells and reservoirs for dual completion on the Altyguyi field.

The main attention in the study of the well and reservoir was paid to the separation of condensate and water from products, as well as work on measuring the determination of the amount of separated condensate from 1 m³ of gas carried out at a complex field installation equipped with mobile block separators. And also the results of complex studies for the period of exploratory drilling and testing of the productivity of drilled gas condensate wells, in steady-state filtration modes of liquid or gas are presented. The results of the conducted studies are necessary for the identification of operational facilities, their drilling systems, taking into account the need for dual completion (DC) in wells.

Keywords: condensate, barometric, pressure recovery curve (PRC), liquid filtration, stationary mode, formula, wellhead.

To study the indicators of a gas condensate field and to determine the amount of condensate released from 1 m³ of gas, as well as conducting gas-hydrodynamic studies in productive wells and formations, were performed by methods and instruments that were used in gas-hydrodynamic studies in oil horizons.

In some wells, for technical reasons, the reservoir and bottom - hole pressure was determined by the barometric formula on uncovered and not lowered depth gauges:

$$P_{b-h.} = P_{b(annul)} \cdot e^s,$$

The separation of condensate and water from the products, as well as work on measuring the determination of the amount of separated condensate from 1 m³ of gas, was carried out at a complex field installation equipped with a mobile block separator of the PBS-350/64 type and a separator of the DEMAG type.

In general, during the period of exploratory drilling and testing of the productivity of drilled gas condensate wells, complex studies were carried out in 11

objects of 5 wells in the established modes of liquid or gas filtration (№ 2, 5, 102, 1, 20). In three wells (№1, 2 and 101), 4 comprehensive studies were carried out on unsteady filtration modes (pressure recovery curve).

The result of working off the PRC for production well № 101 is shown in Fig. 1.

To determine the initial reservoir pressure and temperature of the NK_{7d} horizon, the average reservoir pressure values of 517 kgf/cm² and 87 °C are proposed, which were obtained during the study of the NK_{7d} horizon of the II object of well № 2 and the I object of well №5.

Considering the close location of the NK_{7d} and NK₈ horizons (about 30 m.), the reservoir pressure and temperature were assumed to be P = 517 kgf/cm², T = 87 °C. Work on the determination of condensate indicators and the study of thermodynamic characteristics of wells and reservoirs for both horizons was carried out jointly.

Gas condensate wells and reservoirs were studied in three stationary filtration modes [1].

Fig. 1. Graph of the curve of recovery of bottom-hole pressure to reservoir pressure for production well № 101 at the Altyguyi field

The results of gas dynamic studies and determination of the amount of condensate released from 1 m³ of reservoir gas (gas condensate factor - GCF) are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

The results of field studies to study the gas condensate properties of wells and formations at the Altyguyi field

№ well	Horizon	Perforation interval, (m)	Fitting diameter (mm)	Operation in the mode (hour)	Condensate output (cm ³ /m ³)		Molecular weight of condensate
1	2	3	4	5	6		7
1(II)	NK ₈	3616-3625	12	24	241,9	181,4	-
			10	15	157,4	118,4	-
			-	-	-	-	151,5
			8	8	114,7	88,6	-
			9,5	24	11,7	9,6	-
			8	15	13,9	11,4	-
1(I+II)	NK ₈ +NK ₉	3512-3522 3670-3680	6	15	15,5	12,7	-
			-	-	-	-	150
			10	24	OKH productive		-
			8	18			-
			6	16			-
			6	24	OKH productive		-
			8	22			-
10	20	-					
2(III)	NK _{7d}	3512-3522	8	24	64,6	56,2	-
			-	-	-	-	-
			12	24	-	60,5	159
			8	22	-	29,6	-
			10	18	-	46,3	-
2(III)	NK _{7d}	3512-3522	6,5	24	107,5	93,4	-
			8	18	97,2	81,6	-
			9	15	99,8	86,2	-
			-	-	-	-	159
			9,5	22	14,3	13,1	-
			8	17	12,9	12,0	-
			6	15	23,4	21,5	-
-	-	-	-	-			

1	2	3	4	5	6		7
5(I)	NK 7d	3618-3624	10	20	111,8	102,8	-
			8	21	118,6	104,4	-
			6	15	113,1	101,8	-
			-	-	-	-	144,5
			9,5	20	10,6	8,7	-
			8	21	12,8	10,5	-
			6	15	16,2	13,2	-
			-	-	-	-	153,5
			8	24	50,9	43,8	-
			-	-	-	-	149
			12	24	-	51,4	-
			8	21	-	46,9	-
			10	16	-	46,3	-
101	NK 8	3564-3566	12	24	-	-	-
			10	24	-	-	-
			8	16	-	-	-
20(III)	NK 8	3950-3958	-	-	-	-	-
			9,5	22	-	-	-
			8	17	-	-	-
			6	15	-	-	-
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

The results of hydro - gas dynamic studies of wells and formations of gas condensate deposits were processed using a two - term formula:

$$P_{\text{res.}}^2 = P_{\text{b-h}}^2 = aQ_2 + b \cdot Q_2^2,$$

where: $P_{\text{res.}}$ and $P_{\text{b-h}}$ - respectively, reservoir and bottom-hole pressure, kgf/cm²;

Q_g is the flow rate of separation gas, thousand m³/day;

a and b , respectively, are the coefficients of filtration resistance, depending on the parameters of the bottom-hole zone of the formation and the design of the well bottom.

The flow rate of the reservoir fluid $Q_{\text{res.fl}}$ is calculated using the following formula:

$$Q_{\text{res.fl.}} = Q_{\text{s.g.}} + \frac{Q_{\text{c.}}^{\text{sat}} + G_{\text{eqv.}}}{10^3},$$

$Q_{\text{res.fl}}$ - reservoir mixture, thousand m³/day;

$Q_{\text{s.g.}}$ - flow rate of separated gas, thousand m³/day;

$Q_{\text{c.}}^{\text{sat}}$ - saturated condensate flow rate, m³/day;

G_{eqv} is the calculated gas equivalent of the transfer of the liquid phase (condensate) to the gas phase.

The gas equivalent is determined by the formula

$$G_{\text{eqv.}} = 23342 \cdot \rho / M,$$

Here ρ and M are, respectively, the density and molecular weight of the C_{5+b} fraction.

The value of the molecular weight (μ) of the C_{5+b} fraction is calculated by the formula

$$M = \frac{44,29(\rho_{\text{c.}}^{\text{st.}} + 0,004)}{(1,034 - \rho_{\text{c.}}^{\text{st.}})}.$$

where $Q_{\text{c.}}^{\text{st.}}$ is the density of stable condensate.

Tables 2,3 and 4 show the values of reservoir and well parameters determined when processing the results of gas-dynamic studies and the output of stable condensate for the studied objects.

Table 2

The results of calculations of studies to study the gas condensate properties of wells and formations at the Altygyi field

№ well	Horizon	Perforation interval, (m)	Type of research	Reservoir pressure (kgf/cm ²)	Reservoir temperature (°C)	Stable condensate output (cm ³ /m ³)
1(II)	NK ₈	3616-3625	initial	496	84	119
			regular	452	89	11,4
1(I+II)	NK ₈ +NK ₉	3512-3522 3670-3680	regular	452	91	-
			regular	308	88	-
2(III)	NK _{7d}	3512-3522	regular	510	81	86,2
			regular	490	87	12
			regular	471	82	56,2
			regular	270	81	60,5
5(I)	NK _{7d}	3618-3624	regular	524	84	103
			regular	487	90	8,7
			regular	426	82	43,8
			regular	274	84	51,4
20	NK ₈	3950-3959	regular	400	96	4
			regular	336	87	96,1
101	NK ₈	3564-3566	regular	358	78	85,6

Table 3

The results of calculations of studies to study the gas condensate properties of wells and formations at the Altygyi field

№ well	Horizon	Perforation interval, (m)	Filtration resistance coefficient		Absolutely free gas flow rate (thousand m ³ /day)	Coefficient of gas conductivity (m/sP)	Filtration coefficient (mD)
			a	b			
1(II)	NK ₈	3616-3625	57,7	0,38	732,3	7,87	26,2
			137,6	0,243	677	3,4	11,2
1(I+II)	NK ₈ + NK ₉	3512-3522 3670-3680	86,1	0,411	713	5,37	8,1
			11,0	0,423	460,7	41,7	65,9
2(III)	NK _{7d}	3512-3522	92,5	0,1	1205,5	4,73	14,2
			37,9	0,112	1304,3	12,1	36,3
			-	-	-	-	-
			67,8	0,0123	921,2	6,6	20,0
5(I)	NK _{7d}	3618-3624	187,8	0,194	800,4	2,42	12,1
			80,5	0,111	1144,6	5,74	28,7
			-	-	-	-	-
			93,1	0,0144	725,1	4,9	24,4
20	NK ₈	3950-3959	-	-	-	-	-
			134,4	0,784	303,2	3,4	12,8
101	NK ₈	3564-3566	84,2	0,327	510,4	5,3	79,7

The proposed indicators of stable condensate yield are accepted along the horizon of NK_{7g} -95 cm³/t³; along the horizon of NK₈-118 cm³/t³.

According to the results of measurements, an accelerated drop in reservoir pressure was revealed at the beginning of the operation period [2].

Despite the short period of the start of operation of gas condensate reservoirs, the results of measurements revealed an accelerated drop in reservoir pressure.

For example, well №2 was put into operation in 2009 with an initial reservoir pressure of 510 kgf/cm². In 2010, the reservoir pressure was measured at 490 kgf/cm², and in 2014 it was 270 kgf/cm².

Table 4

The results of the study of the field determination of the properties of stable condensate

№ well	Horizon	Perforation interval, (m)	Fitting diameter (mm)	Condensate output from 1 m ³ of reservoir gas, (cm ³ /m ³)		The rate of entry of the mixture into the barrel is tubing (m/sec)	
				intense	stable		
1(II)	NK ₈	3616-3625	10	157	118	4,95	
			9,5	12	10	4,5	
			10	A light hydrocarbon is oil. The specific gravity is 0.8455 g/cm ³ . Due to the high gas factor, calculations were carried out on gas.			
			6				
2(III)	NK _{7d}	3512-3522	8	97	82	4,1	
			8	13	12	4,3	
			8	65	56	3,5	
			10	-	60,5	4	
5(I)	NK _{7d}	3618-3624	8	119	105	4,1	
			8	13	11	4	
			8	51	44	3,8	
			10	-	46	4	
20	NK ₈	3950-3959	8	-	4	-	
			12	-	55	4	
101	NK ₈	3564-3566	10	-	83	4	

Well № 1 in the gas condensate facility of the NK₈ horizon was put into operation during development with an initial reservoir pressure of 496 kgf/cm² in 2009. In 2014, when measured, its readings amounted to a drop to 306 kgf/cm².

We believe that the reason for the low values obtained during the study is not the creation of an appropriate regime for the separation of products.

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